

ABSTRACT

This mixed-method research design determined the tourists' habits, practices, and emotional responses to Bulabog Putian National Park. The respondents were 100 randomly selected residents/tourists in the Municipality of Dingle. The valid and reliable researcher-made questionnaire checklist was used for tourists' habits, practices, and emotional responses. The data were analyzed using frequency, mean, standard deviation, Kruskal-Wallis, and Spearman rho set at a .05 significance level. Generally, the study revealed that they have a "high" level of practice in tourist habits and practices when classified as to age and employment status. No significant differences existed in assessing tourists' habits according to age and employment status. Kruskal-Wallis H test results showed a significant difference in assessing tourists' practices as to age. Lastly, the data for emotional response revealed that tourists often experience a wide range of emotional responses throughout their travels. These emotions can be influenced by various factors, including the destination, their activities, and personal expectations.

Keywords: *Development management, ecological tourism, tourist habits, tourist practices, emotional response, Bulabog Putian National Park, Dingle, Iloilo*

INTRODUCTION

Tourism has become integral to our globalized world, allowing individuals to explore diverse cultures, breathtaking landscapes, and enriching experiences (Gordon, 2018). However, the increasing influx of tourists worldwide has created the need to understand and promote responsible practices (Cave & Dredge, 2021). As travelers venture into new destinations, they must engage in responsible habits and practices that respect the environment, preserve local cultures, and benefit local communities. By adopting such patterns and practices, tourists can ensure the longevity of their destinations, minimize their impact on natural resources, and contribute positively to the socio-cultural fabric of the host communities. These habits and practices encompass pre-trip research and planning, understanding local customs and traditions, and embracing eco-friendly practices throughout the journey. The significance of responsible tourism practices in fostering a harmonious relationship between tourists and their host environments is uncovered by investigating the impact of these habits, practices, and emotional responses on destinations, local communities, and travelers (Fan, 2023).

Tourism is everywhere (Scheyvens & Hughes, 2021). It is one of the most in-demand economic development tools practiced by most countries, just like the Philippines. As an archipelago, the Philippines has various islands that have individually unique characteristics. Tourists travel for multiple reasons, including exploration, relaxation, and exposure to different cultures, but at the core of that experience lies the destination.

The Philippines offers diverse tourism activities and destinations for tourists with various inclinations; the Philippine tourism industry increasingly plays a significant role in economic development.

Western Visayas is blessed with rich resources, and with its historical and cultural attractions offer ample opportunities for varied activities. The pristine environment setting is excellent for sightseeing, beach holidays, marine sports, hiking, and adventures. It is a place where eco-tourism flourishes and is blessed with abundant natural resources supporting the province. The great thing is that some of the natural areas of Western Visayas are unique, like the Bulabog Putian National Park, Lake Bito, Nautod Wall, and Mt. Manyakiya in Dingle. It will be a big boost to the region's Tourism when eco-tourism is developed. Through the development of eco-tourism in Western Visayas, the status of the area will also grow, and tourists will visit not just for the internationally recognized *Dinagyang* and *Ati-Atihan* but also they can enjoy the eco-tourism destinations Western Visayas has to offer.

Spending time in nature and engaging in nature-based activities can have a range of positive benefits, such as increased well-being, reduced stress levels, and improved physical and mental health (Bratman et al., 2012; Hanna et al., 2019; Mygind et al., 2019; Pasanen et al., 2014).

There are many studies on the antecedents of eco-tourism behaviors, habits, and practices, but the knowledge about factors driving eco-tourism demand still needs to be improved. Therefore, there is a need for further research to explore factors that may drive travelers' intention to visit eco-tourism destinations based on their habits and practices. Such research would lead to a better understanding and, as a result, more effective strategies to foster eco-tourism development.

Along this line, literature is scarce on why tourists visiting a particular place with parks, mountains, and caves motivated the researcher to conceptualize the present study, which aims to examine the tourists' habits, practices, and emotional responses to Bulabog Putian.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. This study utilized mixed methods of qualitative and quantitative research design. This research aimed to cultivate a profound understanding of the perception of tourists' habits, practices, and emotional responses to Bulabog Putian National Park. In understanding the emotional response, the researcher used a qualitative design. Thematic analysis is a method for analyzing qualitative data that entails searching across a data set to identify, analyze and report repeated patterns (Braun & Clarke, 2006). It is usually applied to texts, such as an interview or transcripts. The researcher closely examines the data to identify common themes - topics, ideas, and patterns of meaning that come up repeatedly.

Respondents. The respondents of this study were 100 tourists who visited Bulabog Putian National Park. When the respondents were categorized as to age, 32% were 25 and below, 43% were 26 to 35 years old, 16% were 36 to 45 years old, three 3% were 46 to 55 years old, and 6% were 56 years old and above. When employment status was considered, 17% were contractual, 50% were regular/permanent, 9% were self-employed, and 24% were students.

Data Collection Procedure. The researcher accomplished letters of approval to the Barangay Captains and letters of consent to the respondents before they were allowed to answer the instrumentation. All these steps were done before the study began, during the collection, data analysis, and interpretation of the data. A research-made questionnaire, validated by external experts, was prepared and distributed to the 100 respondents, which were identified via convenient sampling. For the qualitative, the data were taken through one-on-one interviews with audio recordings. Out of 100 respondents, five were chosen to be interviewed. The researcher introduced the topic under study and informed the respondents that they could use any language they were comfortable using in answering questions and that they were free to answer questions as they deemed necessary. The researcher followed the proper health protocols set by the Commission on Higher Education, Department of Health, Department of Education, and Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF) when face-to-face interview needed the following things and actions mainly observed like wearing of face mask, face shield, physical/social distancing, and proper hand washing were strictly followed when face to face interaction is permitted.

Data Analysis Procedure. The quantitative data collected from this study were analyzed statistically to provide answers to the problem adhered to. Frequency count was used to determine the number of respondents in a class or category of the independent variables. Mean was used to assess tourists' habits and practices in Bulabog Putian National Park. Standard Deviation was used to determine the dispersion of the mean as to its homogeneity or heterogeneity of scores. Kruskal-Wallis H Test was used to determine significant differences in the tourists' habits and practices at Bulabog Putian National Park when the respondents were grouped as to age and employment status. Spearman rho was used in determining the relatedness among demographic profiles, tourists' habits, and practices.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The top tourists' habits in Bulabog Putian National Park, when grouped as to age, are reflected in Table 1. In terms of age, the respondents under 25 and below have a "high" level of habits in the following aspects: being law-abiding tourists and respectful of the laws, rules, and regulations of the tourist destination (M=5.00, SD=.000); can personally ask recommendations from friends or family for the advice of the cheap and best tourist destinations to go or visit (M=5.00, SD=.000); can do screenshot important information before traveling (M=4.97, SD=.177); can book cheap flights, resorts, hotels (M=4.94, SD=.246); and love taking an excessive amount of photos or selfies within the area of the tourist destination (M=4.91, SD=.296).

The respondents under the bracket of 26-35 years old have a "high" level of habits in the following aspects: being law-abiding tourists and respectful of the for laws, rules, and regulations of the tourist destination (M=5.00, SD=.000); can personally ask recommendations from friends or family for the advice of the cheap and best tourist destinations to go or visit (M=5.00, SD=.000); can do screenshot important information before traveling (M=4.93, SD=.258); can book cheap flights, resorts,

hotels (M=4.84, SD=.374); and love taking an excessive amount of photos or selfies within the area of the tourist destination (M=4.79, SD=.675).

The respondents under the bracket of 36-45 years old have a "high" level of habits in the following aspects: being law-abiding tourists and respectful of the laws, rules, and regulations of the tourist destination (M=5.00, SD=.000); can asking recommendations from friends or family for the advice of the cheap and best tourist destinations to go or visit (M=5.00, SD=.000); can do screenshot important information before traveling (M=4.94, SD=.250); can book cheap flights, resorts, hotels (M=4.94, SD=.250); and love taking an excessive amount of photos or selfies within the area of the tourist destination (M=4.81, SD=.403).

The respondents under the bracket of 46-55 years old have a "high" level of habits in the following aspects: being law-abiding tourists and respectful of the laws, rules, and regulations of the tourist destination (M=5.00, SD=.000); can personally ask recommendations from friends or family for the advice of the cheap and best tourist destinations to go or visit (M=5.00, SD=.000); can do screenshot important information before traveling (M=5.00, SD=.000); can book cheap flights, resorts, hotels (M=5.00, SD=.000); and love taking an excessive amount of photos or selfies within the area of the tourist destination (M=5.00, SD=.000).

The respondents under the bracket of 56-above years old have a "high" level of habits in the following aspects: being law-abiding tourists and respectful of the for laws, rules, and regulations of the tourist destination (M=5.00, SD=.000); can personally ask recommendations from friends or family for the advice of the cheap and best tourist destinations to go or visit (M=5.00, SD=.000); can do screenshot important information before traveling (M=4.83, SD=.408); can book cheap flights, resorts, hotels (M=4.83, SD=.408); and can do prior research before going to any tourist spots or destinations (M=4.50, SD=.548).

Table 1. Top Tourist Habits as to Age

<i>Statement</i>	Mean	SD	Rank
<i>25 and below</i>			
1. I am law abiding tourist and respectful of the laws, rules, and regulations of the tourist destination.	5.00	.000	1.5
2. I personally ask for recommendations from friends or family for advice on the cheap and best tourist destinations to go to or visit.	5.00	.000	1.5
3. I do screenshot important information before I travel.	4.97	.177	3
4. I book cheap flights, resorts, and hotels.	4.94	.246	4
5. love taking an excessive amount of photos or selfies within the area of the tourist destination	4.91	.296	5
<i>26-35 years old</i>			
1. I am law abiding tourist and respectful of the laws, rules, and regulations of the tourist destination.	5.00	.000	1.5
2. I personally ask for recommendations from friends or family for advice on the cheap and best tourist destinations to go to or visit.	5.00	.000	1.5
3. I do screenshot important information before I travel.	4.93	.258	3
4. I book cheap flights, resorts, and hotels.	4.84	.374	4
5. I love taking an excessive amount of photos or selfies within the area of the tourist destination.	4.79	.675	5
<i>36-45 years old</i>			
1. I am law abiding tourist and respectful of the laws, rules, and regulations of the tourist destination.	5.00	.000	1.5
2. I ask for recommendations from friends or family for advice on the cheap and best tourist destinations to go to or visit.	5.00	.000	1.5
3. I love taking an excessive amount of photos and selfies within the area of the tourist destination.	4.94	.250	3.5
4. I do screenshot important information before I travel.	4.94	.250	3.5
5. I book cheap flights, resorts, and hotels.	4.81	.403	5

46-55 years old

1. I am law abiding tourist and respectful of the laws, rules, and regulations of the tourist destination.	5.00	.000	3.5
2. I personally ask for recommendations from friends or family for advice on the cheap and best tourist destinations to go to or visit.	5.00	.000	3.5
3. I do screenshot important information before I travel.	5.00	.000	3.5
4. I book cheap flights, resorts, and hotels.	5.00	.000	3.5
5. I love taking an excessive amount of photos or selfies within the area of the tourist destination.	5.00	.000	3.5
<i>55 and above</i>			
1. I am law abiding tourist and respectful of the laws, rules, and regulations of the tourist destination.	5.00	.000	1.5
2. I personally ask for recommendations from friends or family for advice on the cheap and best tourist destinations to go to or visit.	5.00	.000	1.5
3. I do screenshot important information before I travel.	4.83	.408	3.5
4. I book cheap flights, resorts, and hotels.	4.83	.408	3.5
5. I do prior research before going to any tourist spots or destinations.	4.50	.548	3.5

The top tourists' habits in Bulabog Putian National Park, when grouped as Employment Status, are reflected in Table 2. For respondents with Contractual Status, they have a "high" level of habits in the following aspects: being law-abiding tourists and respectful of the laws, rules, and regulations of the tourist destination (M=5.00, SD=.000); can personally ask recommendations from friends or family for the advice of the cheap and best tourist destinations to go or visit (M=5.00, SD=.000); can do screenshot important information before traveling ((M=4.88, SD=.332); can do prior research before going to any tourist spots or destinations (M=4.82, SD=.393); and book cheap flights, resorts, hotels (M=4.76, SD=.437).

Respondents with Regular/Permanent status have a "high" level of habits in the following aspects: law-abiding tourists and respectful of the laws, rules, and regulations of the tourist destination (M=5.00, SD=.000); can personally ask recommendations from friends or family for the advice of the cheap and best tourist destinations to go or visit (M=5.00, SD=.000); can screenshot important information before travel (M=4.94, SD=.274); love taking an excessive amount of photos or selfies within the area of the tourist destination (M=4.90, SD=.303); and book cheap flights, resorts, hotels (M=4.84, SD=.370).

Respondents with Self-employed status have a "high" level of habits in the following aspects: being law-abiding tourists and respectful of the for laws, rules, and regulations of the tourist destination (M=5.00, SD=.000); can personally ask recommendations from friends or family for the advice of the cheap and best tourist destinations to go or visit (M=5.00, SD=.000); can screenshot important information before travel (M=4.89, SD=.333); book cheap flights, resorts, hotels (M=4.89, SD=.333); and do prior research before going to any tourist spots or destinations. (M=4.56, SD=.527).

For respondents who are students, they have a "high" level of habits in the following aspects: being law-abiding tourists and respectful of the for laws, rules, and regulations of the tourist destination (M=5.00, SD=.000); can personally ask recommendations from friends or family for the advice of the cheap and best tourist destinations to go or visit (M=5.00, SD=.000); can screenshot important information before travel (M=5.00, SD=.000); book cheap flights, resorts, hotels (M=5.00, SD=.000); and love taking excessive amount of photo or selfies of beautiful spots within the area of the tourist destination (M=4.96, SD=.204).

Table 2. Top 5 Tourist Habits as to Employment Status

Statement	Mean	SD	Rank
<i>Contractual</i>			
1. I am law abiding tourist and respectful of the laws, rules, and regulations of the tourist destination.	5.00	.000	1.5
2. I personally ask for recommendations from friends or family for advice on the cheap and best tourist destinations to go to or visit.	5.00	.000	1.5
3. I do screenshot important information before I travel.	4.88	.332	3
4. I do prior research before going to any tourist spots or destinations.	4.82	.393	3.5
5. I book cheap flights, resorts, hotels	4.76	.437	5
<i>Regular/Permanent</i>			
1. I am law abiding tourist and respectful of the laws, rules, and regulations of the	5.00	.000	1.5

tourist destination.			
2. I personally ask for recommendations from friends or family for advice on the cheap and best tourist destinations to go to or visit.	5.00	.000	1.5
3. I do screenshot important information before I travel.	4.94	.274	3
4. I love taking an excessive amount of photos within the area of the tourist destination.	4.90	.303	4
5. I book cheap flights, resorts, and hotels.	4.84	.370	5
<i>Self-Employed</i>			
1. I am law abiding tourist and respectful of the laws, rules, and regulations of the tourist destination.	5.00	.000	1.5
2. I personally ask for recommendations from friends or family for advice on the cheap and best tourist destinations to go to or visit.	5.00	.000	1.5
3. I do screenshot important information before I travel.	4.89	.333	3.5
4. I book cheap flights, resorts, and hotels.	4.89	.333	3.5
5. I do prior research before going to any tourist spots or destinations.	4.56	.527	5
<i>Students</i>			
1. I am law abiding tourist and respectful of the laws, rules, and regulations of the tourist destination.	5.00	.000	1.5
2. I personally ask for recommendations from friends or family for advice on the cheap and best tourist destinations to go to or visit.	5.00	.000	1.5
3. I do screenshot important information before I travel.	5.00	.000	1.5
4. I book cheap flights, resorts, and hotels.	5.00	.000	1.5
5. I do prior research before going to any tourist spots or destinations.	4.96	.204	5

The top tourists' practices in Bulabog Putian National Park, when grouped as to age, are reflected in Table 3. In terms of age, the respondents under 25 and below have a "high" level of practices in the following aspects; observe conserving water in any tourist destinations (M=5.00, SD=.000); prefer to use long-lasting products (rechargeable batteries, cloth bags) for instead of disposable products (M=5.00, SD=.000); concerned about endangered species and biodiversity (M=5.00, SD=.000); follow travel itinerary (M=5.00, SD=.000); can leave home on time on the day of travel (M=5.00, SD=.000); take into consideration the climate when I schedule my travel (M=5.00, SD=.000); and can see to it that I have an idea of the places where I am going and the distance from one destination to another (M=5.00, SD=.000).

The respondents under the bracket of 26-35 years old have a "high" level of practices with a mean of 5.00, SD=.000 in the following aspects: being able to use long-lasting products (rechargeable batteries, cloth bags) instead of disposable products, concerned about endangered species and biodiversity, follow my travel itinerary, can leave home on time on the day of travel, can take into consideration the climate when I schedule my travel and can see to it that I have an idea of the places where I am going and the distance from one destination to another.

The respondents under the bracket of 36-45 years old have a "high" level of practices with a mean of 5.00, SD=.000 in the following aspects: can avoid using plastic, prefer to use biodegradable bags rather than plastic bags, observe conserving water in any tourist destinations, prefer to use long-lasting products (rechargeable batteries, cloth bags) for an instead of disposable products, concerned about endangered species and biodiversity, follow my travel itinerary, leave home on time on the day of my travel, adhere to my specified time per destination when I travel, take into consideration the climate when I schedule my travel, and see to it that I have an idea of the places where I am going and the distance from one destination to another.

The respondents under the bracket of 46-55 years old have a "high" level of practices with a mean of 5.00, SD=.000 in the following aspects: can always remind my companions that they must observe proper waste disposal of the tourist destinations, avoid using plastic, prefer to use biodegradable bags rather than plastic bags, throw my garbage in the dustbins before leaving the area where I stay, I practiced "CLAYGO" (Clean As You GO), prefer to use long lasting products (rechargeable batteries, cloth bags) for a instead of disposable products, concerned about endangered species and biodiversity, list down the destinations I want to visit, always make an itinerary when I travel, plan ahead on what destinations I would visit, follow my travel itinerary, leave home on time on the day of my travel, choose the shortest route when I travel, take into consideration the climate when I schedule my travel, and see to it that I have idea of the places where I'm going and the distance from one destination to another.

The respondents under the bracket of 46-55 years old have a "high" level of practices with a mean of 5.00, SD=.000 in the following aspects: can always remind my companions that they must

observe proper waste disposal of the tourist destinations, use least number of paper towels to help protect the environment, throw my garbage in the dustbins before leaving the area where I stay, I practiced "CLAYGO" (Clean As You GO), prefer to use long-lasting products (rechargeable batteries, cloth bags) for instead of disposable products, concerned about endangered species and biodiversity, leave home on time on the day of my travel, choose the shortest route when I travel, take into consideration the climate when I schedule my travel, see to it that I have an idea of the places where I am going and the distance from one destination to another.

Table 3. Top Tourists' Practices as to Age

Statement	Mean	SD	Rank
<i>25 and below</i>			
1. I observe conserving water in any tourist destination.	5.00	.000	1.5
2. I prefer to use long-lasting products (rechargeable batteries, cloth bags) instead of disposable products.	5.00	.000	1.5
3. I am concerned about endangered species and biodiversity.	5.00	.000	1.5
4. I follow my travel itinerary.	5.00	.000	1.5
5. I leave home on time on the day of my travel.	5.00	.000	1.5
6. I adhere to my specified time per destination when I travel.	5.00	.000	1.5
7. I take into consideration the climate when I schedule my travel.	5.00	.000	1.5
8. I see to it that I have an idea of the places where I am going and the distance from one destination to another.	5.00	.000	1.5
<i>26-35 years old</i>			
1. I prefer to use long-lasting products (rechargeable batteries, cloth bags) instead of disposable products.	5.00	.000	1.5
2. I am concerned about endangered species and biodiversity.	5.00	.000	1.5
3. I follow my travel itinerary.	5.00	.000	1.5
4. I leave home on time on the day of my travel.	5.00	.000	1.5
5. I take into consideration the climate when I schedule my travel.	5.00	.000	1.5
6. I see to it that I have an idea of the places where I am going and the distance from one destination to another.	5.00	.000	1.5
<i>34-45 years old</i>			
1. I always remind my companions that they must observe proper waste disposal at tourist destinations.	5.00	.000	1.5
2. I avoid using plastic.	5.00	.000	1.5
3. I prefer to use biodegradable bags rather than plastic bags.	5.00	.000	1.5
4. I observe conserving water in tourist destinations.	5.00	.000	1.5
5. I prefer to use long-lasting products (rechargeable batteries, cloth bags) instead of disposable products.	5.00	.000	1.5
6. I am concerned about endangered species and biodiversity.	5.00	.000	1.5
7. I follow my travel itinerary.	5.00	.000	1.5
8. I leave home on time on the day of my travel.	5.00	.000	1.5
9. I adhere to my specified time per destination when I travel.	5.00	.000	1.5
<i>46-55 years old</i>			
1. I always remind my companions that they must observe proper waste disposal at tourist destinations.	5.00	.000	1.5
2. I avoid using plastic.	5.00	.000	1.5
3. I prefer to use biodegradable bags rather than plastic bags.	5.00	.000	1.5
4. I throw my garbage in the dustbins before leaving the area where I stay.	5.00	.000	1.5
5. I practiced "CLAYGO" (Clean As You GO).	5.00	.000	1.5
6. I prefer to use long-lasting products (rechargeable batteries, cloth bags)	5.00	.000	1.5

instead of disposable products.

7. I am concerned about endangered species and biodiversity.	5.00	.000	1.5
8. I list down the destinations I want to visit.	5.00	.000	1.5
9. I always make an itinerary when I travel.	5.00	.000	1.5
10. I plan ahead on what destinations I will visit.	5.00	.000	1.5
11. I follow my travel itinerary.	5.00	.000	1.5
12. I leave home on time on the day of my travel.	5.00	.000	1.5
13. I choose the shortest route when I travel.	5.00	.000	1.5
14. I take into consideration the climate when I schedule my travel.	5.00	.000	1.5
15. I see to it that I have an idea of the places where I am going and the distance from one destination to another.	5.00	.000	1.5

55 - above

1. I always remind my companions that they must observe proper waste disposal at tourist destinations.	5.00	.000	1.5
2. I use the least number of paper towels to help protect the environment.	5.00	.000	1.5
3. I throw my garbage in the dustbins before leaving the area where I stay.	5.00	.000	1.5
4. I practiced "CLAYGO" (Clean As You GO).	5.00	.000	1.5
5. I prefer to read the document on a computer or my mobile device instead of printing it.	5.00	.000	1.5
6. I am concerned about endangered species and biodiversity.	5.00	.000	1.5
7. I follow my travel itinerary.	5.00	.000	1.5
8. I leave home on time on the day of my travel.	5.00	.000	1.5
9. I choose the shortest route when I travel.	5.00	.000	1.5
10. I take into consideration the climate when I schedule my travel.	5.00	.000	1.5
11. I see to it that I have an idea of the places where I am going and the distance from one destination to another.	5.00	.000	1.5

The top tourists' practices in Bulabog Putian National Park, when grouped as to employment status, are reflected in Table 4. For respondents with Contractual Status, they have a "high" level of practices in the following aspects: can avoid using plastic (M=5.00, SD=.000); prefer to use biodegradable bags instead that plastic bags (M=5.00, SD=.000); observe conserving water in any tourist destinations (M=5.00, SD=.000); throw my garbage in the dustbins before leaving the area where I stay (M=5.00, SD=.000); practiced "CLAYGO" (Clean As You GO) (M=5.00, SD=.000); throw my garbage in the dustbins before leaving the area where I stay (M=5.00, SD=.000); concerned about endangered species and biodiversity (M=5.00, SD=.000); prefer to use long lasting products (rechargeable batteries, cloth bags) for a instead of disposable products (M=5.00, SD=.000); follow my travel itinerary (M=5.00, SD=.000); leave home on time on the day of my travel (M=5.00, SD=.000); take into consideration the climate when I schedule my travel (M=5.00, SD=.000); and see to it that I have idea of the places where I'm going and the distance from one destination to another (M=5.00, SD=.000).

For respondents with Regular/Permanent Status, they have a "high" level of practices in the following aspects: can prefer to use long-lasting products (rechargeable batteries, cloth bags) instead of disposable products (M=5.00, SD=.000); concerned about endangered species and biodiversity (M=5.00, SD=.000); follow my travel itinerary (M=5.00, SD=.000); leave home on time on the day of my travel (M=5.00, SD=.000); take into consideration the climate when I schedule my travel (M=5.00, SD=.000); and see to it that I have idea of the places where I am going and the distance from one destination to another (M=5.00, SD=.000).

For respondents with Self-Employed Status, they have a "high" level of practices in the following aspects: is concerned about endangered species and biodiversity (M=5.00, SD=.000); follow my travel itinerary (M=5.00, SD=.000); leave home on time on the day of my travel (M=5.00, SD=.000); see to it that I have idea of the places where I am going and the distance from one destination to another (M=5.00, SD=.000); and search in advance for an alternative way/route in case I am stranded (M=5.00, SD=.000).

For respondents with Student Status, they have a "high" level of practice in the following aspects: can use garbage bags for litter when visiting public parks or open areas (M=5.00, SD=.000); follow my travel itinerary (M=5.00, SD=.000); leave home on time on the day of my travel (M=5.00, SD=.000); adhere to my specified time per destination when I travel (M=5.00, SD=.000); take into consideration the climate when I schedule my travel (M=5.00, SD=.000); and see to it that I have idea of the places where I am going and the distance from one destination to another (M=5.00, SD=.000).

Table 4. Top Tourists' Practices as to Employment Status

Statement	Mean	SD	Rank
<i>Contractual</i>			
1. I avoid using plastic.	5.00	.000	1.5
2. I prefer to use biodegradable bags rather than plastic bags.	5.00	.000	1.5
3. I observe conserving water in tourist destinations.	5.00	.000	1.5
4. I throw my garbage in the dustbins before leaving the area where I stay.	5.00	.000	1.5
5. I practiced "CLAYGO" (Clean As You GO).	5.00	.000	1.5
6. I throw my garbage in the dustbins before leaving the area where I stay.	5.00	.000	1.5
7. I am concerned about endangered species and biodiversity.	5.00	.000	1.5
8. I prefer to use long-lasting products (rechargeable batteries, cloth bags) instead of disposable products.	5.00	.000	1.5
9. I follow my travel itinerary.	5.00	.000	1.5
10. I leave home on time on the day of my travel.	5.00	.000	1.5
11. I take into consideration the climate when I schedule my travel.	5.00	.000	1.5
12. I see to it that I have an idea of the places where I am going and the distance from one destination to another.	5.00	.000	1.5
<i>Regular/Permanent</i>			
1. I prefer to use long-lasting products (rechargeable batteries, cloth bags) instead of disposable products.	5.00	.000	1.5
2. I am concerned about endangered species and biodiversity.	5.00	.000	1.5
3. I follow my travel itinerary.	5.00	.000	1.5
4. I leave home on time on the day of my travel.	5.00	.000	1.5
5. I take into consideration the climate when I schedule my travel.	5.00	.000	1.5
6. I see to it that I have an idea of the places where I am going and the distance from one destination to another.	5.00	.000	1.5
<i>Self-Employed</i>			
1. I am concerned about endangered species and biodiversity.	5.00	.000	1.5
2. I follow my travel itinerary.	5.00	.000	1.5
3. I leave home on time on the day of my travel.	5.00	.000	1.5
4. I see to it that I have an idea of the places where I am going and the distance from one destination to another.	5.00	.000	1.5
5. I search in advance for an alternative way/route in case I am stranded.	5.00	.000	1.5
<i>Student</i>			
1. I use garbage bags for litter when visiting public parks or open areas.	5.00	.000	1.5
2. I follow my travel itinerary.	5.00	.000	1.5
3. I leave home on time on the day of my travel.	5.00	.000	1.5
4. I adhere to my specified time per destination when I travel.	5.00	.000	1.5
5. I take into consideration the climate when I schedule my travel.	5.00	.000	1.5
6. I see to it that I have an idea of the places where I am going and the distance from one destination to another.	5.00	.000	1.5

Kruskal-Wallis H test results showed a significant difference in the tourists' practices as to age [H(4) = 21.678; p=.000]. The two-tailed probability of .000 is less than the set alpha level of .05. Multiple comparisons test revealed that the significance was between respondents aged 55 years old and above and 25 years old and below; between 55 years old and above and 36 to 45 years old and finally, between 55 years old and above and 26 to 35 years old. Results further implied that tourists' practices differ in age.

However, no significant differences were noted in the tourists' habits as to age [H(4) = 5.664; p=.226] and employment status [H(3) = 5.793; p=.122] and tourists' practices as to employment status [H(4) = 4.083; p=.253]. The two-tailed probabilities of .226, .122, and .253 are more significant than the set significance level of .05 alpha.

Table 5. Differences in the Habits and Practices of Tourists as to Age and Employment Status

Sources of Variations	df	Mean Rank	H _{value}	Sig. (2-tailed)	Interpretation
<i>Tourists' Habits</i>					
<i>Age</i>					
25-below		56.72			
26-35		46.94			
36-45	4	52.34	5.664	.226	Not Significant
46-55		64.33			
55 - above		31.00			
<i>Employment Status</i>					
Contractual		43.32			
Regular/Permanent	3	47.66	5.793	.122	Not Significant
Self-employed		47.83			
Students		62.50			
<i>Tourists' Practices</i>					
<i>Age</i>					
25-below		50.52			
26-35		56.93			
36-45	4	56.63	21.678*	.000	significant
46-55		10.67			
55 - above		7.92			
<i>Employment Status</i>					
Contractual		58.15			
Regular/Permanent	3	52.02	4.083	.253	Not Significant
Self-employed		35.28			
Students		47.63			

Spearman's rho test result showed no significant relationship between the tourists' habits and practices [$\rho = -.032$; $p = .755$]. The two-tailed probability of .755 is greater than the set alpha level of .05. The results further implied that tourists' habits do not influence their practices.

Table 5. Relationship between Tourists' Habits and Practices

Variables	ρ_{value}	Sig. (2-tailed)	Interpretation
<i>Habits</i>			
<i>Practices</i>	-.032	.755	Not Significant

THEME 1: Reason to travel

Excerpt 1

Informant 1: nag adto ko sa bulabog putian because:: Lenten season tuya and and upod ko: is: akon nga family hhh

English Translation: We went to Bulabog Putian because it was Lenten Season, and I was with my family.

Informant 2: I visited Bulabog Putian national park .hhh during our tree planting activity when I was a: SSG officer or Supreme Student Government during my high school days.

Informant 3: ahhm: gusto ko Makita ang iya natural beauty and uhmm (1.3) aside sa natural beauty na (.) may ara sila da nga isa ka species nga viper nga man-og nga ara kuno ga stay and ang aton da nga mga ano (.) mga caves.

English Translation: I want to see natural beauty, and aside from it, they have one species of viper that stays there, and also, there are caves.

Informant 4: We always visit Bulabog every holy week. Because there are a lot of caves and we took pictures, and there is a: century OLD tree (.) it is located there.

English Translation: I want to be one with nature even for one day only to remove stress from work.

Analysis: The informants have their own reason for going to the destination, like the time of year, but also mainly because Bulabog Putian National Park is rich in natural beauty and biodiversity.

Theme 2: Use of Social Media as an aid to promote the destination

Excerpt 1

Informant 1: yes mam/ I'll go: especially if Makita mo sa picture nga makaakit ang isa ka lugar kag i: name lagawan syempre ma tempt kaw man nga mag adto tuy a kag i: maglagaw sa lugar nga da

English Translation: Yes, mam, I will go, especially if that place is very inviting and a nice place to frolic, then it is very tempting to go there.

Informant 2: It is a yes, mam (0.2) .hhh; as a traveler and as an active on social media, I saw some photos or videos uploaded on the internet that amazed me and made me: interested in that beautiful place.

Informant 3: YES ah. Yes gid.

English Translation: Yes, yes, of course.

Informant 4: Ahmm: it depends on the PHOTO on how THEY take: It Ilke something like its: a DECENT photo: but honestly speaking, yeah, I could: I would travel: I would LOVE to travel to Bulabog Putian.

Informant 5: huo ah, KAY sang: una daan ang: (0.5) syempre subong Makita mo ang: POST nga ginafeature ang bulabog tapos Makita mo ang mga uhmm kahoy tapos puro GREEN tih manami gid nga ma tistingan mag adto:

English Translation: Yes, because we can see posts about Bulabog, and you can see trees of green, and it is nice to try and go there.

Analysis: All informants stated they are willing to go to Bulabog Putian based on Social Media postings. Bulabog Putian National Park can be a photographers' and nature lovers' dream destination with its beautiful landscapes and unique animals. They can take beautiful pictures and learn about the park's attractions by exploring it.

Theme 3: Experiences

Excerpt 1

Informant 1: so pagkadto namon sa bulabog a::ng pagsaka namon tuya nagvisit kami sang different caves tapos gin explore man namon ang kasulok sulokan sang bulabog mam (.)

English Translation: So, when we went there to hike, we visited the different caves, and then we explored Bulabog.

Informant 2: WHEN (1.2) When I was there (.) I captured the moment at the summit of the mountain (.) and saw the beauty of nature and:: inside of (h) caves.

English Translation: When I was there, I captured the moment at the summit of the mountain and saw the beauty of nature and inside the caves.

Informant 3: nagvisit kami didto sa bulabog: bali nag ano kami sa mga caves nila< ginpanglantaw man namon ang: kun ano nga formation dyan nga Makita.

English Translation: We visited Bulabog to see the caves and the formation.

Informant 4: ahmm:: first of all, SYEMPRE nagtravel kami halin sa banwa .hhh paadto sa Bulabog (.) pag abot namon, nag: register kami KAG nagBAYAD entrance FEE then after nag saka nA. may mga signs kun ano nga wAy ang mga kuweba kag: ang mga century old tree ma:labayan mo man. Bali ano: sightseeing kag walking inobra namon: KAG picture syempre.

English Translation: First of all, we traveled from the town proper. Then we registered and paid the entrance fee, and proceeded to hike. There are signs leading us to the caves, and we pass by the century-old trees. Sightseeing and walking were the main activity we did, and picture taking, of course.

Informant 5: sa pag-abot, ginpaSULAT kami sa BLUE nga logbook: para mag sulat ka ngaran mo kag kun taga diin ikaw(.) tapos ahmm: mangkuton kun gusto nga may imaw ((tour)) guide (0.3) hay indi kami ka tultul abi ((smile))= (0.10)

Picture malang ya:: amon nga ano: ubra tapos syempre pamati sa ((tour guide)) tapos panaw.

English Translation: Upon arrival, we were tasked to write our names and address in the BLUE logbook, and we were asked if we wanted a tour guide because we were not familiar with the site. We took pictures, listened to the tour guide, and walked.

Analysis: All informants shared their experiences visiting Bulabog Putian. Informants 1,2,3, and 4 mainly did spelunking, and Informant 5 did sightseeing.

Theme 4: Damages in the destination

Informant 1: so paglagaw namon sang time nga to mam< syempre indi gid malikawan pagduro tawo pati ang ang basura damo man.

English Translation: So, when we went there, that time there was a flock of tourists, and of course, there was lots of garbage.

Informant 2: nakita ko gid didto is: ang ginakaingin bala gid kay indi man naton gid mabantayan to sa mga liblib gid nga parte kag may panimalay GID sa palibot nahimo nila nga source (of income) ang uling, amo na.

English Translation: I saw kaingin farming because we cannot always guard the place, especially on the residential side around; they use charcoal as a source of income.

Informant 3: ahmm ang una gid siguro ang ano ang WASTE(.) Garbages within the vicinity↑ and then: ang about sa trees bala like: damo bala ang kwan nga illegal logging kay te damo daan di kahoy ((kag panimalay)) sa palibot tapos ang last is because magdamo ang tawo indi na ma sunod maintain KAG ma control ang tawo nga naga adto kag saka.

English Translation: The first one would be waste, Garbage in the vicinity, and then illegal logging since there are many trees everywhere, and last is because of a flock of people coming, control and maintenance in the are neglected.

Informant 4: may mga maagyan kami nga Kahoy nga hanggod .hhh century old nga kahoy nga hhh ang mga ugat nanda: tama ka LAPAD kag tama ka ahmm: hanggod .hhh teh Makita ang vandalism ka iban nga mga turista (.) gina drawingan nanda. Makita gid ang sulat sa ugat ka kahoy.

Analysis: 4 out of 5 respondents revealed the harm of tourism to Bulabog Puti-an National Park. Informants 1 and 3 revealed that improper garbage disposal was experienced there. Meanwhile, Informants 2 and 4 talked about illegal logging and kaingin farming that can disrupt ecosystems, displace wildlife, and threaten biodiversity.

Theme 5: Ways to minimize and avoid damage

Excerpt 1

Informant 1: with regards sa basura ang ma think dyan nga option is if ever man magsaka sila sa bulabog and ila nga food tani kag ang ila water is Ang reusable dapat ang ila gamiton para indi nanda basta basta lang ma dispose sa area tuya kag kun magdala man sila pagkaon nila.

English Translation: Regarding garbage, I think of an option that if ever they will hike in Bulabog, they will only bring reusable food and water containers to avoid improper disposal.

Informant 2: ahmm ang mga basura mam kun pwede nga maka provide sanda ENOUGH trash bins along the track sa kun diin ga agi ang mga ga hiking kag pwede man nga may ga bantAy sa mga pirme naadtunan nga AREA ka bukid para ma sita ang mga pasaway(.)

English Translation: With regards to waste disposal, they will provide enough trash bins along the track if possible – where the hikers will pass by, and if allowed, some employees will be in charge of guarding the areas in the mountain to reprimand those who are not following the rules.

Informant 3: pa bantayan gid (0.2) kag multahan para ma disiplina ((ang waay gapati)).

English Translation: Guard the area and give fines to discipline the lawbreakers.

Informant 4: FIRST of all: proper ano::: (0.8) i-briefing GID ang tau:o didto BEFORE mag↑sulod sa bulabog: nga like::: amo na anG RULES and REGULATIONS first. INDI gid sila mag-diretso like::: wala briefing sa mga guest nga: amo na ang tourist spot: and then like pwede magrequire tourist guide sa mga pangaYAW: para ma guide sila althrough out KAG ma tahap sila mag tinunto(.) THAT's it

English Translation: First, give the people a briefing about the rules and regulations before hiking in Bulabog. Never allow guests to proceed if they will not undergo briefing. Moreover, require first-time visitors with tour guides to guide and not play around the site.

Informant 5: kun damo daad ang tawo I limit danay nanda: OR hulaton manaog ya nagsaka PARA waay it overcrowding nga matabo.

English Translation: If there are many tourist hiking – limit the entry for the meantime or wait for the hikers to finish to avoid overcrowding.

Analysis: All informants revealed ways to avoid or limit the damage being done (if any) in Bulabog Putian. Informants one and two emphasized that waste disposal might be adequately done if there are enough bins for the hikers to throw their trash. Informants three and four discussed briefing the hikers/tourists visiting Bulabog Putian and punishing those not abiding by the law. Informant number five suggested not allowing the hikers to hike at one time to avoid overcrowding.

CONCLUSION

It appears that the study's respondents were impacted internally, such as by their objectives and motivations, or externally, such as by societal trends and suggestions.

Bulabog Putian National Park has vast potential in terms of eco-tourism which could bring about economic, social, and environmental development in the town of Dingle and the whole of Western Visayas. Therefore, it is essential for the local government to strengthen its support for promoting and developing the eco-tourism destination.

Age, Sex, Place of Residence, and Employment status were factors found not to influence one's assessment of Tourists' habits, practices, and emotional responses to Bulabog Putian.

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